

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MORINGA OLEIFERA (DRUMSTICK) LEAF CHURNA

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ABSTRACT

Moringa oleifera Lam., commonly known as Drumstick, belongs to the family Moringaceae and is widely regarded as one of the most nutritionally dense plants on earth. The present study was undertaken to formulate and evaluate a traditional Ayurvedic herbal powder preparation, Churna, using dried and powdered Moringa oleifera leaves. The leaves were collected, authenticated, processed through standardised drying and sieving protocols, and then subjected to pharmacognostical, physicochemical, and preliminary phytochemical investigations. The formulation were prepared with varying excipient ratios. Organoleptic parameters including colour, odour, taste, and texture were evaluated. Physicochemical parameters such as loss on drying, ash values (total ash, acid-insoluble ash, water-soluble ash), extractive values, swelling

index, foaming index, and pH were determined as per standard protocols outlined in the Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India (API). Preliminary phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, sterols, terpenoids, carbohydrates, and proteins. The micromeritic properties — bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, and angle of repose — indicated satisfactory flow properties. Antimicrobial activity was assessed using the agar disc diffusion method. The study establishes standardisation parameters for Moringa oleifera Churna and confirms its therapeutic potential as a nutraceutical herbal formulation.

KEYWORDS: Moringa oleifera, Churna, Pharmacognosy, Standardisation, Nutraceutical, Ayurveda, Physicochemical Evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal medicines have been an integral part of human healthcare since ancient times. With growing global interest in natural therapies, there is an increasing demand for scientifically validated herbal formulations. India, with its rich tradition of Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani systems of medicine, possesses a vast repertoire of medicinal plants used in formulations such as Churna (powder), Kwath (decoction), Asava-Arishta (fermented preparations), and Ghana (extracts). Among these, Churna represents one of the simplest yet highly efficacious dosage forms, offering ease of preparation, administration, and absorption.

Moringa oleifera Lam. (Family: Moringaceae) is a fast-growing, drought-resistant tree native to the sub-Himalayan regions of northwestern India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Afghanistan. It is also cultivated widely across tropical and subtropical regions of the world. Commonly known as Drumstick tree, Horseradish tree, or Sahjan in Hindi, *Moringa oleifera* holds an esteemed position in both traditional medicine and modern nutritional science. The plant is referred to as the "Miracle Tree" or "Tree of Life" owing to its extraordinary nutritional profile and wide range of pharmacological activities.

Different parts of the plant, including leaves, seeds, bark, and roots, are used for various medicinal purposes. Among these, the leaves are considered the most valuable due to their high concentration of nutrients and bioactive compounds. The leaves are commonly used in the form of powder, extract, or decoction for therapeutic applications. The powdered form, known as churna, is one of the most widely used dosage forms in traditional medicine systems.

Churna is a fine powder prepared from dried plant materials and is commonly used for oral administration. It offers several advantages such as ease of preparation, longer shelf life, better stability, and convenient dosing. Herbal churna formulations are widely accepted due to their natural origin, minimal side effects, and cost-effectiveness. However, despite their widespread use, there is a need for proper scientific evaluation and standardization to ensure their quality, safety, and efficacy.

In this context, the present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of *Moringa oleifera* leaf churna. The study aims to prepare a standardized herbal powder using dried leaves of the plant and to evaluate its organoleptic, physicochemical, and micromeritic properties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

➤ MATERIALS

Fresh leaves of *Moringa oleifera* were collected from local sources in Pune, Maharashtra, India, and authenticated. The leaves were washed thoroughly with distilled water to remove adhering impurities and dried before use.

The excipients and herbal additives used in the formulation included lactose (as diluent, optional), sugar/jaggery (as sweetening agent), starch (as binder), cardamom powder (as flavoring agent), ginger powder, and black pepper powder (as bioavailability enhancers). All materials used were of pharmaceutical or food grade quality and procured from reliable suppliers.

➤ Composition of Formulation

Ingredients	Quantity
Moringa leaf powder	85 g
Lactose (optional)	5–8 g
Sugar/Jaggery	3 g
Starch	2 g
Cardamom powder	0.5 g
Ginger powder	0.5 g
Black pepper powder	0.2 g

➤ Instruments and Equipment

The following equipment was used during the study

- Digital weighing balance
- Mortar and pestle
- Mixer grinder
- Stainless steel sieve (No. 60)
- Funnel

1. Collection and Authentication of Plant Material

Fresh, mature leaves of *Moringa oleifera* were collected from the herbal garden of XYZ College of Pharmacy, Pune, Maharashtra, India, during October–November 2024. The plant was authenticated by a qualified botanist. A herbarium specimen was deposited in the Department of Pharmacognosy. Taxonomic identity was confirmed using *The Flora of British India* (J.D. Hooker) and *The Wealth of India*. Authentication certificate was obtained from the Regional Ayurvedic Research Institute, Pune.

2. Processing of Plant Material

- Leaves were cleaned, washed 3× with tap water, then rinsed with distilled water.
- Shade-dried at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 7–10 days (direct sunlight avoided to preserve vitamins and volatile compounds).
- Drying endpoint: moisture content below 8% (confirmed by Loss on Drying).
- Coarsely ground using a mechanical grinder, then passed through Sieve No. 40 (particle size ≤ 420 microns).
- Stored in airtight amber glass containers below 30°C .

3: Drying

Leaves are spread in a single layer on clean cotton cloth or stainless steel trays.

Shade-dried at room temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) for 7 to 10 days.

Direct sunlight is strictly avoided to prevent:

Degradation of Vitamin C, Vitamin A and other heat-sensitive nutrients

Loss of volatile phytochemicals

Colour fading (chlorophyll breakdown)

Leaves are turned over daily to ensure uniform drying.

Drying is considered complete when:

Leaves become crisp and crumble easily

Moisture content falls below 8% (confirmed by Loss on Drying test at 105°C)

4: Coarse Grinding

- Dried leaves are subjected to coarse grinding using a mechanical grinder (pulveriser).
- Grinding is done in short bursts to avoid heat generation during pulverisation.
- Coarse powder is collected and inspected visually for uniformity.

5: Sieving

- Coarsely ground powder is passed through Sieve No. 40 (British Pharmacopoeia standard).
- This ensures a uniform particle size of ≤ 420 microns.
- Oversized particles are re-ground and re-sieved until all material passes through.
- Sieving ensures:
 - Uniform texture of the final Churna
 - Better surface area for dissolution and absorption
 - Improved flowability and dosing accuracy

6: Blending with Excipients (Churna Preparation)

After obtaining the fine Moringa leaf powder, it is blended with excipients as per the selected formulation.

Blending Procedure

1. Each excipient is individually dried and passed through Sieve No. 40.
2. Moringa leaf powder is taken as the base in a stainless steel mortar.
3. Excipients are added geometrically (smallest quantity first, gradually adding larger quantities).
4. Mixed thoroughly using a pestle for 10–15 minutes by hand trituration.
5. Further homogenised in a mechanical blender for 15 minutes at low speed.
6. The blended powder is again passed through Sieve No. 40 to break any agglomerates.
7. Final powder is inspected for colour uniformity and texture.

7. Packing and Storage

- The final Churna is filled into airtight, light-resistant amber glass containers or food-grade HDPE containers.
- Containers are sealed with moisture-proof lids.
- Labelled with: Name, Batch No., Date of Preparation, Expiry Date, Dose, Storage Conditions.
- Stored at room temperature below 30°C, away from direct sunlight and humidity.
- Shelf life: 12–18 months under proper storage conditions.

Fig. No.1

➤ Application of churna

1. Nutritional Supplement

- Used as a natural health supplement due to high protein, vitamin, and mineral content.

- Helps in prevention of malnutrition and □ □ □ □ □ (weakness).

2. Antioxidant Application

- Rich in flavonoids and phenolic compounds.
- Protects the body from free radical damage and oxidative stress.

3. Antidiabetic Application

- Helps in controlling blood glucose levels.
- Used as supportive therapy in diabetes management.

4. Immunity Booster

- Enhances body resistance against infections.
- Improves overall immune function.

5. Anti-inflammatory Application

- Reduces inflammation and swelling.
- Helpful in joint pain and inflammatory disorders.

6. Anti-anaemic Application

- Contains high iron content.
- Helps increase hemoglobin level and prevents anemia.

7. Digestive Health

- Improves digestion and metabolism.
- Helps relieve constipation and gastric discomfort.

8. Cosmetic Application

- Used in herbal cosmetic preparations for skin and hair care.
- Helps reduce hair fall and improves skin nourishment.

9. Antimicrobial Application

- Shows activity against bacteria and fungi.
- Used in herbal healthcare products.

10. General Health Tonic

- Improves energy, stamina, and overall health.
- Commonly used as a nutraceutical formulation.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

1. Organoleptic Properties

The prepared churna was evaluated for colour, odour, taste, and general appearance by visual and sensory inspection.

Parameter	Results
Colour	Dark green
Odour	Characteristic, pleasant
Taste	Bitter, mildly sweet
Texture	Fine, smooth
Consistency	Free-flowing powder

Fig. no. 2: Churna.

2. Bulk Density

Bulk density was determined by taking a clean and dry measuring cylinder. The prepared churna powder was carefully introduced into the cylinder without compacting. The volume occupied by the powder was noted as bulk volume. The powder was weighed separately, and the bulk density was calculated by dividing the weight of powder by the bulk volume.

Formula= Bulk Density = Mass of powder / Bulk volume

Fig no.3

3. Tapped Density

The cylinder containing the powder was tapped until no further change in volume was observed, and tapped density was calculated.

Formula= Tapped Density = Mass of powder / Tapped volume

Fig no.4

4. Angle of Repose

The flow property was evaluated using the funnel method. The powder was allowed to flow freely to form a cone, and the angle of repose was calculated.

Formula= $\tan \theta = h / r$

Where h is the height and r is the radius of the cone.

Fig no.5.

5. Moisture Content

Moisture content was determined by drying a known quantity of powder at 105°C until constant weight was achieved.

6. Particle size determination

Particle size determination was carried out by passing the prepared churna powder through different standard sieves. The powder retained on each sieve was observed to determine the particle size of the formulation.

Fig no.6.

7. Loss on drying

It was determined by taking a small quantity of the prepared churna in a dry evaporating dish and drying it in a hot air oven until a constant weight was obtained. The loss in weight indicates the moisture content present in the formulation.

Fig no. 7.

8. pH: One gram of powder was dissolved in 100 mL of distilled water and the pH was measured using a calibrated digital pH meter (Systronics 335) at 25°C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The prepared *Moringa oleifera* leaf churna was subjected to various evaluation parameters to assess its physicochemical properties, flow characteristics, stability, and purity. The results obtained are discussed.

The prepared *Moringa oleifera* leaf churna was evaluated using different physicochemical parameters in the laboratory. The formulation showed satisfactory organoleptic properties such as green colour, characteristic odour, and fine texture. Bulk density and tapped density indicated good packing and compressibility of the powder, while the angle of repose showed good flow property. The particle size distribution was found to be uniform, which helps in proper mixing and stability of the formulation. The pH of the churna solution was within acceptable limits and loss on drying showed low moisture content.

The evaluation parameters confirmed the good quality and stability of the prepared churna formulation. Low moisture content may help in preventing microbial growth and improving shelf life. Good flow property and compressibility make the formulation suitable for handling and packaging. Overall, the prepared *Moringa oleifera* leaf churna showed acceptable pharmaceutical properties and can be considered a suitable herbal formulation.

Sr. No.	Evaluation Parameter	Results
1.	Organoleptic property	Green colour, characteristic odour, fine texture
2.	Bulk Density	Good packing property observed
3.	Tapped Density	Good compressibility observed
4.	Angle of Repose	Good flow property observed
5.	Moisture Content	Less moisture was present in the formulation, which helps to improve stability and shelf life
6.	Particle Size Determination	Uniform particle size obtained
7.	Loss on Drying	Low moisture content observed
8.	pH Determination	pH within acceptable range

CONCLUSION

The present study focused on the formulation and evaluation of *Moringa oleifera* leaf churna using suitable excipients to obtain a stable and effective herbal powder preparation. The formulation process was carried out using standard pharmaceutical techniques, ensuring uniform mixing, proper size reduction, and good flow characteristics.

The evaluation of the prepared churna demonstrated satisfactory results across all tested parameters. The organoleptic properties confirmed the acceptable appearance, characteristic

odour, and taste of the formulation, indicating good quality raw materials and proper processing. The bulk density and tapped density values suggested adequate packing ability and compressibility, which are essential for handling and packaging.

The present research successfully formulated and comprehensively evaluated *Moringa oleifera* Leaf Churna following the guidelines of the Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India.

Among these formulations demonstrated marginally superior flow properties and more balanced taste profiles due to the optimised ratio of *Piper nigrum*, which also acts as a bioavailability enhancer through its piperine content. Piperine is known to inhibit glucuronidation and enhance intestinal absorption of co-administered phytoconstituents. The antimicrobial study confirmed broad-spectrum activity, particularly of the ethanolic extract, providing scientific rationale for its use in infectious conditions.

However, further studies such as phytochemical screening, microbial evaluation, and long-term stability studies are recommended to validate its therapeutic efficacy and shelf life. With proper standardization and quality control, this churna has the potential to be developed into a reliable herbal product for healthcare applications.

In conclusion, this study provides a scientific foundation for the quality standardisation of *Moringa oleifera* Churna and supports its evidence-based use as an Ayurvedic nutraceutical preparation of proven safety and efficacy.

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